

ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF PATIENTS WITH BRAIN TUMORS AFTER RADIATION THERAPY

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Relevance. The number of oncological diseases is growing from year to year. This is due to the widespread use of computer-based visualized research methods in the modern world. Brain tumors occupy a special place among oncopathology. The treatment of brain tumors is an urgent problem of modern neuro-oncology, since the survival rate of patients remained low until recently, and the disease itself led to an increase in cases of disability and a decrease in quality of life. Along with surgical and drug treatment methods, radiation therapy is currently widely used, which allows for long-term remission, even complete recovery, in some diseases. Modern innovative methods of radiation therapy in combination with other types of therapy undeniably increase the survival of patients, especially with primary brain tumors. The main goal of radiation therapy is to increase the effectiveness of targeted impact on the tumor with minimal radiation exposure to healthy organs and tissues. Radiation therapy for brain tumors can be performed using whole brain radiation therapy (WBRT), classical conformal radiation therapy, stereotactic radiation surgery (SRS), stereotactic radiation therapy (SRT).

The effectiveness of radiation therapy against tumor cells is achieved by high doses of ionizing radiation, which in turn increases the risk of developing radiation necrosis (RN) of brain tissue in the irradiated area. The risk of ROP also increases with the volume of brain parenchyma and the radiation dose.

Keywords: brain, radiation therapy, single focal dose, total focal dose, IMRI, 3D-CRT, VMAT, SRS, DGT

Objective: to conduct an analytical structured analysis of the data of patients who received radiation for primary brain tumors.

Materials and methods: 333 patients underwent a retrospective and prospective analysis of their medical records from 2018 to 2024 with an assessment of the results of radiation therapy. All patients were treated with

Elekta infinity linear accelerator and Terabalt 100 cobalt system using various radiation techniques such as 3D conformal radiation therapy (3D-CRT), intensity modulated radiation therapy (IMRT), volumetric dose modification with rotational therapy (VMAT), stereotactic radiosurgery (SRS), external gamma therapy (EGT). Radiation therapy was planned by a radiation oncologist and a medical physicist. Patients received a single focal dose (SFD) of 2.09 ± 0.05 Gy (1.8-14 Gy) on average once a day for 5 days and a total focal dose (TFD) of 52.56 ± 0.57 Gy (18-69.9). Pre-radiation preparation was carried out using CT simulators (Siemens - Somatom difinished AC) with mandatory immobilization of the patient using an individually designed thermoplastic mask (Orfit). The volume of irradiation and the choice of the type of irradiation were determined individually after a thorough collection of the anamnesis, tumor localization, the volume of the operation performed, and MRI and CT data.

Results: Out of 333 patients who received radiation therapy, 178 patients (53.4%) were alive. The number of deceased patients was 155, which corresponds to 46.6% of cases. Of these, 93 are men and 62 are women. 53 people (34.1%) died in the first year after radiation therapy. The results showed that in men, the majority of deaths were observed in those who received IMRT (70% of patients). In addition, 14% (13 cases) of deceased patients were treated with VMAT, 12% (11 people) with 3D, 3% (3 people) with DHT, and 1% (1 patient) with SRS. Among women, the number of deaths was 49 (79%) after IMRT, 8 cases (13%) after VMAT, 4 cases (6%) after 3D, and 1 case (2%) after DHT. The high mortality rates after IMRT can be explained by the highest number of patients using this method in cancer patients. In continuation of the analysis of fatal cases, we studied the most common localization of brain tumors. In deceased men, in an equal percentage of cases (24% each), the tumor was localized in the frontal and temporal regions, 5 men (5%) had a cerebellar tumor. In 18 women (29%), the tumor was in the frontal lobe of the brain, in 7 (11%) - in the temporal region, in 6 (10%) - a cerebellar tumor.

Conclusions:

More men died (58.4%) after radiation therapy compared to women (41.6%). The highest number of deaths in both men and women occurred in the first year after radiation therapy. The most common tumor localization in men is the frontal and temporal lobes, and in women, the frontal lobe.

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